

No-cement Refractory Shotcrete and Gunning Mixes

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This work focuses on the development of microsilica-gel bonded no-cement shotcrete and dry-gunning mixes using two speciality products, SioxX-Flow as deflocculant and SioxX-Set as accelerator. Critical installation properties were first investigated in laboratory-scale, then full-scale shotcreting and dry-gunning trials were carried out by industrial partners. The sprayed panels were cut and used for mechanical and hot-properties evaluations. The results demonstrate that cement-free, shotcreted and dry-gunned microsilica-gel bonded mixes not only exhibit good installation properties and low rebound, but also provide enhanced hot-properties compared to low-cement castables (LCCs).

1 Introduction

A variety of installation techniques have been developed for different application areas of refractory castables, evolving from traditional casting using moulds, to time saving options such as conventional dry gunning and shotcreting (also sometimes referred to as wet-gunning) [1–2]. In dry-gunning the water is added at the nozzle and the interaction time is short, therefore, dry-gunning normally exhibits higher rebound and more dust than shotcreting. However, dry-gunning is a well-proven installation technique for smaller repairs and is often a cost-saving procedure. Generally shotcreting provides more homogenous properties, does not generate dust, has very low rebound and high efficiency with output up to 10–15 t/h. Furthermore, the water content is strictly controlled since all water is added during the mixing process prior to the actual shotcreting.

It is well known that the mix design (particle size distribution, dispersants and accelerators) is essential for successfully installing refractory materials by either dry-gunning or shotcreting. In addition, good practices (such as selection of an appropriate pump, nozzle and experienced installation team) is of the utmost importance. A number of research papers have been published during

the last 30 years, of which most have been focusing on equipment and accelerators, using low-cement castables (LCCs) or ultra-low cement castables (ULCCs) [3–7]. Shotcreting and dry-gunning of NCCs have not been widely applied due to the challenges of controlling setting and green strength.

The first shotcrete (called wet-gunning) method for cement-free refractory castables was demonstrated in 1999 in Japan by Iwasaki et al. [8]. Recently, silica-sol bonded shotcreted NCCs have been used for blast furnace main troughs [9] and in cement plants [10]. However, handling, storage and use of liquid silica-sol are logistic factors that must be dealt with, especially at lower temperatures, which limits the application of silica-sol bonded NCCs. Furthermore, silica-sol bonded NCC, is of course not suitable for dry-gunning installation.

Obviously, a technology based on a “dry-version” silica binder, using microsilica powder, is of great interest. Recent reports disclose that a genuine bond based on microsilica coagulation is created, and that the setting of microsilica-gel bonded castables is caused by cations, a similar set mechanism to colloidal silica [11].

In this paper, compositions of bauxite based NCCs for shotcreting and dry-gunning installation were designed using microsilica-

gel as binder system in combination with two speciality products, SioxX-Flow and SioxX-Set. SioxX-Flow works as a multi-functional dispersant for microsilica-containing aluminosilicate LCCs, ULCCs and NCCs. It is also suitable for shotcreting application. SioxX-Set is designed for undispersed systems such as gunning mixes, but can also be used as accelerator for LCCs and ULCCs. Our mixes were first tested in the laboratory to check the workability. Then, several full-scale shotcreting and dry-gunning trials were carried out in cooperation with industrial partners. Finally, the mechanical properties, hot-properties and bond mechanism were evaluated in comparison to LCCs.

2 Experimental

2.1 Mix design

The particle size distributions (PSDs) were calculated using the EMMA program in order to achieve a suitable workability [12]. EMMA uses the Andreassen model and is widely used to evaluate and optimize particle packing in all types of castables. In the present study, the q-values for shotcreting and dry-gunning mixes are 0,27 and 0,22, respectively.

Tab. 1 shows the composition of bauxite based mixes for shotcreting and dry-gunning. Bauxite, brown sintered alumina (BSA), kyanite and calcined alumina with different particle size fractions were selected as aggregates. Calcined alumina, cement

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Keywords: shotcreting, dry-gunning

Tab. 1 Bauxite based NCC and LCC for shotcreting and gunning.

%	Shotcreting		Dry-Gunning	
	NCC-S	LCC-S	NCC-G	LCC-G
Bauxite 0,5–6 mm	52	52	37,5	37
BSA 96 0–0,5 mm	15,5	16	23	22
TA 60 0–0,3 mm	15	15	5	5
Calcined alumina fines	10	5	12,5	10
CA cement 70 % Al ₂ O ₃	0,5	5	0,5	5
Elkem Microsilica 971	6	6	6,5	7,5
EMSIL-DRY	0,1	0,1		
SioxX-Flow	1	1		
Reactive alumina			7,5	7,5
Rawkyanite 35 mesh			5	5
Betonite			0,5	0,5
SioxX-Set			2	0,5
Water	4,5	5,0	8	9

increase of the diameter of the fresh mix measured 90 seconds after removing the cone.

2.3 Industrial-scale shotcrete and dry-gunning trials

Based on the results from the laboratory, full-scale shotcreting and dry-gunning trials were carried out in cooperation with industrial partners. 500 kg mixes of each recipe is shown in Tab. 1 were prepared. The water addition for dry-gunning mixes was 8–9 %, and the water in NCC-S and LCC-S for shotcreting was 4,5–4,8 % and 5,0–5,3 %, respectively. The mixes were sprayed without complications and test panels produced. The rebound for both shotcreting and dry-gunning was considered low by the installation crews.

No lamination was observed in the centre of the panels and samples were cut for further characterisation. Figs. 2a,b show a test panel and cut specimens. The cut specimens were fired at various temperatures before cold crushing strength (CCS), cold modulus of rupture (CMOR) and hot modulus of rupture (HMOR) measurements.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Evaluation of NCC and LCC shotcrete

Self- and vibration-flow values of lab-scale samples are shown in Fig. 3. The NCC-S had similar flow values at 4,5 % water addition as the LCC-S at 5,0 % water. The self-flow value of NCC-S was 52 % and the vibration-flow was 112 %. The consistency of NCC-S looked fine, no bleeding or separation was observed as seen in Fig. 4.

3.2. Evaluation of NCC and LCC for dry-gunning

The mixes listed in Tab. 1 were first evaluated according to the lab procedures. The NCC-G mix showed similar good consistency and stickiness as the LCC-G mix.

Fig. 5 shows the development of ultrasonic velocity in the lab-scale mixes as a function of time from mixing. As stiffness and speed of sound are closely related, the increase in velocity indicates end of working time and initial set. As seen, the microsilica-gel bonded NCC-G exhibits almost as fast gel-

Fig. 1 NCC-G dry-gunning mix under evaluation in the laboratory. a) Ball in hand and b) Balls sticking to the glass wall

and other additives were used in the matrixes. SioxX-Flow (Elkem/NO) was used as specialty dispersant in the shotcrete recipes, and SioxX-Set (Elkem/NO) was used as accelerator in the dry-gunning recipes.

2.2 Laboratory test procedures

To design the dry-gunning mixes, the following test procedure was used for lab evaluation. i) mix it in a Hobart mixer, ii) stop mixing as soon as the dry mix starts to wet, iii) make a ball in hand to evaluate its consistency and iv) throw the ball onto a glass wall. If it sticks, it passes the test; if it slips, it fails.

To develop shotcrete recipes, the flow and setting-behaviour were evaluated in the lab. Self-flow and vibration-flow were measured using the 50 mm high flow-cone described in ASTM C230. The self-flow value is the %

Fig. 2 Panel and cut specimens of NCC-G a) Panel (500 x 500 x 100 mm) b) Cut specimens (25 x 25 x 150 mm) for HMOR test

Fig. 3 Self-flow (SF) and vibration-flow (VF)

Fig. 4 Vibration-flow testing of microsilica-gel bonded NCC-S. The LCC-S looked similar

ling and hardening process as LCC-G, even though the final velocity was lower.

3.3 Mechanical strength

The sprayed panels were prefired at 600 °C before cutting with the exception of NCC-G, which was fired at 1000 °C since it was too weak to cut. The cut specimens were

fired for 12 h at 1000, 1200, 1300 and 1400 °C before testing. CCS and CMOR of NCC mixes are summarized in Figs. 6, 7, and the LCC-S and LCC-G are included for comparison.

Surprisingly, the CCS of NCC-S is higher than LCC-S at firing temperatures in the range of 600-1200°C, as seen in Fig. 6. The

CCS of microsilica-gel bonded NCC-S fired at 1000°C is ~85 MPa, while the LCC-S only reaches ~60 MPa. The better performance can perhaps be attributed to 0,5 % lower water addition in the NCC-S. At temperatures above 1200°C, the CCS of both NCC-S and LCC-S are at the same level. Concerning the dry-gunned specimens, the

Fig. 5 Setting and hardening of NCC-G and LCC-G.

Fig. 6 CCS of cut specimens after firing at various temperatures

Fig. 7 CMOR of cut specimens after firing at various temperatures.

Fig. 8 Bulk density of cut specimens after firing at various temperatures

Fig. 9 Apparent porosity of cut specimens after firing at various temperatures

Fig. 10 HMOR of cut specimens at various test temperatures

CCS is much lower at given temperature. CCS of the NCC-G is 40-50 MPa at temperatures >1000°C, which is only about half of NCC-S. As shown in Fig. 7, CMOR follows as expected the same trend as CCS.

The CCS and CMOR of shotcreted specimens are about double that of the dry-gunned ones while the water addition is half compared to the gunning mix. Obviously, it is very important for refractory producers to consider various factors in order to choose the right installation techniques and the right binder system.

3.4 Bulk density (BD) and apparent porosity (AP)

The BDs and APs of the sprayed mixes after firing for 12 h at 600, 1000, 1200, 1300 and 1400 °C are summarized in Figs. 8, 9. BDs of NCC-S are in the range of 2,75–2,81 g/cm³, slightly higher than that of LCC-S. The BDs of NCC-G are in the range of 2,55–2,60 g/cm³, slightly higher than LCC-G. This is as expected due to mix composition and higher water addition in

the LCC-S and LCC-G. Concerning different installation technology, the shotcreted specimens exhibits much higher BDs than those of dry-gunned ones. This is mainly attributed to the high-water addition in dry-gunned specimens and the better compaction achieved in shotcrete.

As shown in Fig. 9, the porosity of both NCC-S and LCC-S decreases with increasing firing temperature and the porosity of the NCC-S is slightly lower than that of the LCC-S. The minimum porosity of the sprayed NCC-S is 17,2 %, corresponding to a bulk density of 2,81 g/cm³, while the porosity of the LCC-S is 19,8 % at 1200 °C, corresponding to a bulk density of 2,78 g/cm³. LCC-S exhibits slightly higher bulk density than the NCC-S, while the porosity is similar after firing at 1400 °C. This is probably attributed to liquid formation where the liquid fills the pores and is also the reason for the improved CCS and CMOR of LCC-S after firing at 1400 °C, as seen in Figs. 6, 7. The porosity of dry-gunned NCC-G after firing at temperature of 600–1400 °C is in the range

of 24,9–25,8 %, much lower than those of LCC-G (in the range of 28,5–30,4 %). This indicates that less water is used for installation of NCC-G compared to LCC-G.

3.4 Hot-properties

HMOR results are shown in Fig. 10. At 1000 °C, the HMOR of NCC-S is ~15 MPa, significantly higher than that of LCC-S. With increasing temperature, up to 1400 °C, HMOR for LCC-S drops continuously, probably due to liquid formation between microsilica and cement. For NCC-S, alumina, silica and calcium (from the 0,5 % cement added as coagulating agent) form a liquid phase that causes the material to soften and loose strength up to around 1200 °C. A similar HMOR strength development is observed for NCC-G and LCC-G.

As seen in Fig. 10, the HMORs for NCC-S and NCC-G reach their lowest value at 1200 °C. At higher temperatures NCC-S and NCC-G have better hot strength than LCC-S and LCC-G. At 1400 °C, the HMOR of NCC-S is ~3,5 MPa, about 100 % higher than LCC-S. The improved HMOR is attributed to mullite formation, which is in line with our previous findings [11].

3.5 SEM characterisation

Cut specimens of LCC-S and NCC-S were chosen for further SEM characterisation, in order to look at the bond mechanism of microsilica-gel bonded NCC compared to LCC at elevated temperatures. Figs. 11, 12 show micrographs after HMOR testing at 1200 and 1400 °C, respectively. At 1200 °C, needle-like mullite is observed in the matrix of LCC-S while only trace amount of mullite

Fig. 11 SEM micrographs of etched fractured surfaces of cut specimens fired at 1200 °C, a) LCC-S and b) NCC-S

is found in the microsilica-gel bonded NCC-S. This is probably attributed to the formed liquid phase from cement and microsilica at 1200 °C that facilitates local mullite formation in LCC-S, which leads to higher HMOR compared to NCC-S (Fig. 10).

At 1400 °C, numerous mullite crystals are observed in both LCC-S and NCC-S, as shown in Fig. 12. However, the difference is that the needle-like mullite in LCC-S are single crystals after the glassy phase has been etched away, but the ones in NCC-S are interlocked and closely packed. This indicates that little liquid phase is formed in NCC-S whereas a large amount of liquid is formed in LCC-S at 1400 °C. The mullite in LCC-S is embraced by the liquid phase and the strength deteriorates as soon as the liquid phase begins to form. On the contrary, for NCC-S, the needle-like mullite crystals provide strength by bridging the aggregates, forming a strong and highly refractory matrix.

4 Conclusions

Microsilica-gel bonded NCC and cement bonded LCC were successfully shotcreted and dry-gunned and the properties were compared. The results confirm that microsilica-gel bonded NCCs exhibit as good workability as LCCs and that installation techniques have strong impact on mechanical properties. The mechanical strength of the shotcreted NCC-S is approximately 100 % higher than the dry-gunned NCC-G. Compared to LCC, the microsilica-gel bonded NCC exhibits high mechanical strength at test temperatures from 600 °C upwards. Due to mullite formation and less liquid formed at 1400 °C, the HMOR of the microsilica-gel bonded NCC is approximately double that of LCC. Furthermore, SEM mi-

Fig. 12 SEM micrographs of etched fractured surfaces of cut specimens fired at 1400 °C, a) LCC-S and b) NCC-S

crographs of sprayed samples confirm that mullite formation and minimal liquid phase are essential to give excellent thermo-mechanical properties. When the cement content is increased (LCC), mullite crystals may be embraced by liquid phase and will not contribute to hot strength.

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